

Public participation in decisions about public health and social measures used to manage the Covid-19 pandemic: protocol for a systematic review

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ABSTRACT

Background

During the Covid-19 pandemic, governments and health authorities have had to make difficult decisions about public health and social measures such as social distancing, face masks, travel restrictions, self-isolation, quarantines, lockdowns, and vaccination. Judgments underlying those decisions require democratic input, as well as expert input.

Objective

To systematically review examples of participatory democracy in decisions by governments and health authorities about how to control the Covid-19 pandemic, including the level or degree of participation, inclusion of marginalised groups, the methods used for participation, the decision-making process, support for understanding and applying relevant concepts for making well-informed decisions, and evaluation of the effects of participation.

Methods

We will include reports that describe public participation in deliberations or decisions by a government, public health authority, or international agency about public health and social measures used to manage the Covid-19 pandemic, including case reports and any type of qualitative or quantitative evaluation. We will search Participedia, MEDLINE, Embase, IPSA, Sociological Abstracts, ProQuest Politics Collection, CPSI-S, CPSI-SSH, Web of Science Core Collection, Clarivate Analytics, Citationchaser, and relevant websites, including Open Government Partnership, the International Observatory on Participatory Democracy, and Involve. Two review authors will independently read the titles and abstracts resulting from the search process and eliminate any obviously irrelevant reports. We will retrieve the full text of potentially relevant reports. Two review authors will then assess each retrieved report for inclusion. One review author will extract data from each included report using a standard data-extraction form. A second review author will check the extracted data against the full report. If possible and warranted, we will contact report authors to collect information that is missing from reports. For formal evaluations that report effects of participation on an outcome, we will use the “Risk of Bias In Non-randomised Studies - of Interventions” (ROBINS-I) tool to assess the risk of bias. We will undertake a structured synthesis.

KEYWORDS

participatory democracy, public participation, citizen participation, health policy, policy making, Covid-19, infection prevention and control, public health and social measures, pandemic, epidemic, systematic review

BACKGROUND

During the Covid-19 pandemic, governments and health authorities have had to make difficult decisions about public health and social measures such as social distancing, face masks, travel restrictions, self-isolation, quarantines, lockdowns, and vaccination. Decisions needed to be made quickly, with limited evidence of the effects of prevention and control measures and important trade-offs between the potential benefits and harms.¹ Although these decisions affected nearly everyone, some if not most of the time, there appears to have been little participation of those affected in deliberative or decision-making processes about public health and social measures.²

One reason for this is that participation takes time, especially if it is not already institutionalised,³ and decisions needed to be made quickly. On average, democratic governments were slower than autocratic ones to implement (and enforce) restrictive measures.⁴ A likely explanation for this is that democratic governments had to consider a trade-off between health impacts and democratic rights and (in addition to the trade-off between health impacts and economic consequences), and elected officials needed to consider their chances of being re-elected, unlike their autocratic counterparts. In democracies, rights are seen as important, and individuals are entitled to join debates and make informed decisions. Nonetheless, in democracies during a public health crisis, there is a tendency for the executive branch of government to expand its power and for the elevation of public health experts.⁵ Moreover, many people in democracies may prefer strong leadership and technocratic governance when there is a public health crisis.⁶

The justification for actions taken by governments and public health authorities, their empowerment, and the lack of participation is embedded in the precautionary principle: in response to urgent and credible threats of serious harm, proportionate precautions should be taken. This is a complex principle that requires judgements about the urgency of a threat, the credibility of the threat, the likelihood and seriousness of the potential harms, and the potential benefits and harms of interventions.⁷ Those judgments require democratic input, not just expert input.⁸⁻¹⁰ In addition, those judgements should be informed by the best available evidence, and application of the precautionary principle should include scientific evaluation to reduce important uncertainties when evidence is lacking.¹¹

As noted in the Alma-Ata Declaration from the International Conference on Primary Health Care, “The people have the right and duty to participate individually and collectively in the planning and implementation of their health care.”¹² In addition to being a democratic right, participation in deliberative and decision-making processes (“participatory democracy”) has the potential to improve the quality of the judgements and decisions that are made, build trust, improve adherence, and help to ensure transparency and accountability.⁸ Engaging members of the public can help to ensure that:¹³

- Their concerns are heard and considered
- Problems are analysed, described, and perceived correctly
- Appropriate solutions are identified
- Important barriers to implementing solutions are considered
- Effective implementation strategies are identified
- Appropriate values are used when weighing the pros and cons of options
- Policy decisions are appropriate, understood, and acceptable
- Marginalised communities are included in decision making

Public engagement may also help to ensure that important uncertainties are identified and addressed.¹⁴

However, public participation may not always be helpful. Poorly planned and implemented participation can create mistrust, waste people's time, and undermine future attempts at participatory democracy.¹⁵ Participation without clear objectives may anger participants and fail to add benefit to the policymaking process or outcomes. Care should also be taken not to use participation for inappropriate reasons. Sometimes, for example, participation may simply be used to legitimise decisions that have already been made behind closed doors, and people may be misled into believing they are able to affect the decision. Similarly, public participation should not be used simply to allow authorities to avoid responsibility for difficult decisions.

Factors that can determine the effects of participation

The extent to which the potential benefits of participation are achieved, and potential harms are avoided is likely to depend on several factors, including:

- Inclusive representation
- an appropriate level of participation with clear expectations
- use of effective methods for participation
- use of a systematic and transparent decision-making process
- critical thinking
- evaluation

Each of these is discussed below.

Inclusive representation

Unequal voter turnout is likely to be biased against less well-to-do citizens.¹⁶ Participation in deliberative and decision-making processes also is likely to be unequal and biased against people with less education and lower socio-economic status.¹⁷ Participatory innovations may be used mainly by the more privileged groups that already have more opportunities to have an impact on decision-making, and marginalised communities may be left out.

Level of participation

Different circumstances require different levels of engagement, and these have been conceptualised in several ways. The "[spectrum of participation](#)" developed by the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2)¹⁸ includes the following options:¹³

- informing (one-way information dissemination, including information about the process used to make decisions, e.g., online publication of the policy and its basis, press releases, press conferences)
- consulting (e.g., elicitation of written comments or responses to questions, question and answer sessions, open phone lines, interviews, focus groups, surveys, public hearings),
- involving (interactive discussion and dialogue which supplement internal decision-making processes, e.g., working groups, policy dialogues, or other deliberative processes
- collaborating (members of the public "at the table" and active as team members in deliberations, but not involved in final decision, e.g., advisory groups, task forces, consensus processes), and
- empowering people (decisions by a group or organisation of stakeholders with specific authorisation and delegation of authority to make decisions).

In addition to the goal of participation for each level, the IAP2 spectrum describes what the public or stakeholders can expect at each level.

Methods for participation

In addition to the level or degree of participation, methods used for participation can vary with respect to diverse social, cultural, and political contexts and how people are recruited and selected, the type of communication, and training and support:^{19, 20}

Decision-making processes

Public health decision making is complex. The processes that decision makers use, the criteria they use to reach a decision, and the evidence that they use to inform their judgments are often unclear. They may not have clear criteria for deciding, omit important criteria, give inappropriate importance to other criteria, or not use the best available evidence to inform their judgements. Systematic and transparent systems for decision making can help to ensure that all important criteria are considered and that the best available evidence informs judgements about each criterion.^{21, 22} Important criteria for public health decisions include:²²

- the importance of the problem
- whether the desirable effects outweigh the undesirable effects, which depends on:
 - the anticipated desirable and undesirable effects of the options,
 - how much people value the affected outcomes, and
 - the certainty of the evidence
- whether the net benefits are worth the cost, which depends on:
 - the resource requirements, and
 - the certainty of the evidence of resource requirements
- the distribution of benefits, harms, and costs and impacts on equity
- whether the option is acceptable
- whether it is feasible to implement the option

Critical thinking

Democracy and well-informed policy decisions depend on critical thinking, the ability to think clearly and rationally about what to do or what to believe.²³ Good decisions make effective use of the information available to the decision maker at the time the decision is made. The aim of critical thinking is to increase the probability of correct judgements and good outcomes, but many other factors affect outcomes besides critical thinking.²⁴

Critical thinking about interventions - things that people can do - depends on understanding and applying basic concepts or principles for evaluating the trustworthiness of claims about the effects of interventions and evidence of the effects of interventions, and for making well-informed decisions.²⁵ Not understanding and applying those concepts can result in believing and supporting or acting on unreliable claims. For example, a survey of Norwegian adults found that respondents did not understand or apply basic concepts such as:²⁶

- Beliefs alone about how interventions work are not reliable predictors of the presence or size of effects.
- Comparison groups should be as similar as possible in evaluations of interventions.

Participants in deliberative or decision-making processes should be assisted to understand and apply basic concepts such as those. If they lack understanding and they are not provided with support or help understanding and applying relevant concepts, it can adversely affect those processes.

Evaluation

Because the potential benefits and harms of different approaches to achieving participatory democracy are uncertain, they should be evaluated.

Previous and ongoing systematic reviews

Kemper and colleagues reviewed studies of patient and public engagement in decision making regarding infectious disease outbreak management.² They searched PubMed, Embase, PsycInfo, the Web of Science Core Collection, and Scopus on 7 July 2020 and found 13 studies that met their selection criteria. Only one of the studies was a randomized trial. None of the included studies focused on the Covid-19 pandemic. Most papers described their efforts as a first step, and no structural embedment of collective participation in decision-making regarding outbreak management was identified.

Other previous systematic reviews with a broader focus also have found limited evidence of the effects of public involvement in healthcare planning and policy.^{20, 27-31} Other systematic reviews have explored multi-stakeholder activities to control Covid-19,³² integrating citizen engagement into evidence-informed health policymaking,³³ citizen juries in health policymaking,³⁴ online citizen participation in deliberation and policymaking,³⁵⁻³⁷ deliberative minipublics,^{38, 39} approaches to broaden the diversity of consumers engaged in guideline development,⁴⁰ the effect of municipality size on political efficacy and participation,⁴¹ and evaluation tools for patient and public engagement in research and health system decision making.⁴²

We searched PROSPERO⁴³ 3 August 2022 for systematic review protocols that had participat*, involve*, or engag* in the title and had Covid-19 as the health area of review. We found several related review protocols, but none with the same objective as this review.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷ At least one more broader review of public involvement in health policymaking is also underway, with a focus on contextual factors affecting participation and the performance of different methods.⁴⁸

OBJECTIVE

The aim of this review is to inform decisions about how best to enable public participation and deliberation in decisions about public health and social measures, and to inform decisions about evaluations of participatory democracy in the context of pandemics and epidemics.

The objective is to systematically review examples of participatory democracy in decisions by governments and health authorities about how to control the Covid-19 pandemic, including:

- the level or degree of participation,
- inclusion of marginalised groups,
- the methods used for participation,
- the decision-making process,
- support for understanding and applying relevant concepts for making well-informed decisions, and
- evaluation of the effects of participation

We will address the following questions:

1. What methods for participation have been used?
2. What has been the level or degree of participation and to what extent was there inclusive representation?
3. What are the purported effects of the methods that have been used?
4. To what extent have structured decision making processes been used, with explicit criteria?

5. To what extent were participants able to critically appraise claims and the evidence that was considered, and make informed choices?
6. How have participatory innovations been evaluated?

METHODS

Selection criteria

Types of studies

We will include reports that describe public participation in deliberations or decisions by a government, public health authority, or international agency about public health and social measures used to manage the Covid-19 pandemic, including case reports and any type of qualitative or quantitative evaluation.

We will include reports of democratic initiatives that were not formally connected with a decision-making process, but that aimed to support public participation in deliberations (for example, initiatives by civil society organisations). We will exclude reports with major gaps in the description of the initiative (e.g., “stubs” in Participedia).

Types of participants

We will include reports that describe public participation in deliberative or decision-making processes by international agencies (e.g., WHO or another UN organization), national, subnational (e.g., provincial or state), or local (e.g., community or municipal) governments or public health authorities (e.g., institutes or departments). Members of the public includes citizens or members of communities affected by the decision. We will include a focus on diverse communities with differentiated access to the health system and marginalised communities that tend to be left out of mainstream participatory processes.

We will exclude reports that describe the methods used by committees that include experts, elected officials, or public health professionals without public participation. We will exclude reports that describe participation in deliberative or decision-making processes by health service providers or professional organizations. We also will exclude reports that describe participation in deliberative or decision-making processes about clinical interventions (e.g., treatments for Covid-19 patients).

Types of interventions

We will include reports that describe methods used to consult, involve, collaborate with, or empower the public in deliberations or decisions about public health and social measures.

We will exclude reports that describe methods used only to inform the public; surveys undertaken without any other public participation; methods used to influence decisions in a particular direction (for example, by advocacy groups) rather than to support public participation; community engagement focused on provision of services by the community rather than public participation in deliberations or decisions by a government, public health authority, or international agency; and patient and public involvement in research.

Types of outcome measures, language, and publications

We will not include or exclude reports based on the reporting of outcomes, the language, or publication status.

Search methods

We will search Participedia for cases that include “Covid”. Participedia is a collaborative, digital learning tool for the co-production of knowledge about new forms of citizen participation across the world (www.participedia.net).⁴⁹ It contains over 2000 cases documenting specific examples of how various methods of participatory politics and governance are implemented. A simple search 9 August 2022 using “Covid” yielded 127 cases.

We also will search MEDLINE, EMBASE, Sociological Abstracts, SIGLE (System for Information on Grey Literature in Europe), NTIS (the USA government’s National Technical Information Service), PAIS (Public Affairs Information Service) International and CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, IPSA (International Political Science Abstract), and Citationchaser (Additional file 1). In addition, we will search relevant websites, including the International Observatory on Participatory Democracy (<https://oidp.net/en/index.php>) and Involve (<https://www.involve.org.uk/>).

Data collection

Selection of studies

Two review authors will independently read the titles and abstracts resulting from the search process and eliminate any obviously irrelevant reports. We will retrieve the full text of potentially relevant reports. Two review authors will then assess each retrieved report using the selection criteria described above. For search results from MEDLINE and other bibliographic databases, we will use [Covidence](#) for screening the search results and full text reports. For Participedia and other sources, we will use a spreadsheet.

We will include reports meeting all the selection criteria. We will resolve disagreements by consensus of all the authors. The review authors will divide up responsibility for carrying out screening of searches and assessment of the full text of retrieved reports.

We will prepare a table listing the included reports, the purpose of the initiative, the context, and the methods for participation. We will also prepare a table of excluded reports. This will include reports that appear to be relevant based on the title and abstract but are excluded after consideration of the full-report text and the reasons for exclusion.

Data extraction

For each included report, we will extract the following information:

- the level or degree of participation
- the purpose of the initiative
- the context
 - the location
 - the dates
 - the institutional base, organiser, and funder of the initiative
- who participated, how they were recruited, and the degree of substantive community inclusion in the participatory initiative
- the methods for participation
 - interactions among participants
 - training and support of participants
 - what information was provided to participating members of the public and how
- the decision-making process that the participation feeds into

- what if any criteria were considered and whether the criteria were explicit or implicit
- what judgements participants were asked to make
- how judgements by participants were used in decisions or recommendations
- who made decisions or recommendations and was there direct participation in making decision or recommendation
- critical thinking
 - whether participants expected to or given the opportunity to think critically about the options being considered, and if so:
 - what if any consideration was given to the ability of participants to think critically about the options being considered
 - what if any support was given to participants to help them critically appraise or understand critical appraisal of relevant claims and evidence, or to make informed judgements about the options being considered
 - whether the basis for judgements by experts was explained to the public in plain language
- evaluation
 - whether a formal evaluation was done (i.e., an evaluation using explicit methods)
 - if so, what were the main findings
 - what was the risk of bias for reported effects (see below)
 - whether any outcomes, influence on decisions or recommendations, or effects reported that were not based on a formal evaluation and if so, their basis
 - reported lessons learned and the basis for those

One review author will extract data from each included report using a standard data-extraction form. A second review author will check the extracted data against the full report. For Participedia cases we will review the references that are cited and search for additional reports. If possible and warranted, we will contact report authors to collect information that is missing from reports.

Risk of bias

For formal evaluations that report effects of participation on an outcome), we will use the “Risk of Bias In Non-randomised Studies - of Interventions” (ROBINS-I) tool to assess the risk of bias.⁵⁰

In addition, we will assess whether the report authors provide adequate information to allow us to judge the applicability of the findings to other settings.

Data synthesis

We will undertake a structured synthesis.⁵¹ We will start by preparing a spreadsheet with the following information: the methods used to involve the public, reported effects, the basis for the purported effects, and the risk of bias. The methods used to involve the public will include the level of participation, how members of the public were recruited and selected, the forum for communication, and training and support provided to participating members of the public.

1. What methods have been used?

To address the first question, we will use framework analysis,^{52, 53} guided in part by Veri’s analysis of cases in Participedia,⁵⁴ and following the stages of familiarisation, coding, charting and interpretation of the data. Two of the investigators will independently review the data. They then will group the

methods reported in each case into the four groups shown in Table 1 (based on Veri's four clusters of democratic innovations), but also considering modifications to these categories of innovations.

*Table 1. Categories of democratic innovations**

Category	Participants	Communication	Output
Consensus processes	Restricted, representative, and inclusive (e.g., stratified random selection)	Interactive (face-to-face or online)	A consensus
Public meetings	Limited, not necessarily representative, and inclusive (e.g., election or appointment)	Interactive (face-to-face or online)	A count, vote, or summary of the participants' views
Informal online processes	Voluntary	Informal online communication with little interaction	Support for a proposal
Voting (referenda or online voting)	Voluntary	No interaction	A decision

* Based on Veri's analysis of cases in Participedia⁵⁴

All the review authors will then review the categorisation of innovations. Disagreements will be resolved by discussion. The definitions and boundaries of each category will be discussed among the review authors and the framework for categorising innovations will be revised in line with the categories that emerge from the data. We will then chart the data by writing a summary of the data for each category of innovations. Finally, using the summarised data, we will explore the range and nature of potential democratic innovations.

2. What has been the level or degree of participation and to what extent was there inclusive representation?

We will describe the level or degree of participation and the extent to which there was inclusive representation for each category of democratic innovations and explore variation within and across categories.

3. What are the purported effects of the methods that have been used?

We will summarise the purported effects of each category of innovations in tables and assess the certainty of the evidence for the main findings using the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) system.⁵⁵

4. To what extent have structured decision making processes been used, with explicit criteria?

We will prepare a spread sheet with the following data for each report: the criteria that were used, whether they were explicit or implicit, the judgements participants were asked to make, the information provided to participants to inform their judgements, how their judgements were used in decisions, who decided, and whether participants participated directly in decisions about public health and social measures. We will then summarise the findings in a table and describe the extent to which elements of a structured decision-making processes were used and variation in the decision-making processes that were used within and across categories of democratic innovations.

5. To what extent were participants able to critically appraise claims and the evidence that was considered, and make informed choices?

We will prepare a spread sheet with the following data for each report: whether participants were expected to or given the opportunity to think critically about the options being considered, whether consideration given to the ability of participating members of the public to think critically about the options being considered, whether support was given to participants to help them critically appraise (or understand critical appraisals of) relevant claims and evidence, whether support was given to participants to help them make informed judgements about relevant public health and social measures, and whether the basis for judgements by experts or decision makers were explained to participants in plain language. We will then summarise the findings in a table and describe the extent to which participants were able to critically appraise claims about effects and make well-informed decisions. We will also describe variation within and across categories of democratic innovations.

6. How have participatory innovations been evaluated?

We will prepare a spread sheet with the following data for each formal evaluation: the question(S) addressed, the methods that were used, and the risk of bias. We will then summarise the findings in a table and describe gaps in the questions that have been addressed and the methods that have been used. We will also describe variation within and across categories of democratic innovations and identify potential priorities for future evaluations.

Public participation in this review

We will invite activists and practitioners in the Participedia community to comment on a draft of this protocol and to join an online discussion group where they can ask questions and make suggestions, and where we can present interim results and ask questions. We will invite them to comment on a draft of the review and to participate in online meetings where the results will be discussed.

DECLARATIONS

Protocol registration and amendments

This protocol was registered with PROSPERO September 8, 2022, ID 358991. All protocol amendments will be numbered sequentially, dated, and recorded in PROSPERO.

Availability of data and other materials

Extracted data will be archived in Zenodo (<https://about.zenodo.org/>) when the results are published.

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Competing interests

The review authors have no competing interests.

Author contributions

ADO prepared the first draft of this protocol. All the authors read, provided feedback, and approved the final manuscript. ADO is the guarantor.

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REFERENCES

1. Glasziou PP, Michie S, Fretheim A. Public health measures for covid-19. *BMJ*. 2021;375:n2729. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n2729>
2. Kemper S, Bongers M, Slok E, Schoonmade LJ, Kupper J, Timen A. Patient and public engagement in decision-making regarding infectious disease outbreak management: an integrative review. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2021;6(11). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2021-007340>
3. Lacelle-Webster A, Landry J, Smith AMD. Citizen voice in the pandemic response: democratic innovations from around the world. In: Smith G, Hughes T, Adams L, Obijiaku C, editors. *Democracy in a Pandemic*. London: University of Westminster Press; 2021. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1v3gqz6.24>
4. Cheibub JA, Hong JYJ, Przeworski A. Rights and deaths: government reactions to the pandemic. Available at SSRN 3645410. 2020. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3645410>
5. Parry LJ, Asenbaum H, Ercan SA. Democracy in flux: a systemic view on the impact of Covid-19. *Transform Gov: People Process Policy*. 2021;15(2):197-205. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TG-09-2020-0269>
6. Amat F, Arenas A, Falcó-Gimeno A, Muñoz J. Pandemics meet democracy. Experimental evidence from the COVID-19 crisis in Spain. *SocArXiv*. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/dkusw>
7. Weir E, Schabas R, Wilson K, Mackie C. A Canadian Framework for Applying the Precautionary Principle to Public Health Issues. *Canad J Public Health*. 2010;101(5):396-8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03404860>
8. Norheim OF, Abi-Rached JM, Bright LK, Bærøe K, Ferraz OLM, Gloppen S, et al. Difficult trade-offs in response to COVID-19: the case for open and inclusive decision making. *Nat Med*. 2021;27(1):10-3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-01204-6>
9. Birch J. Applying the precautionary principle to pandemics. *PhilPapers*; 2021. <https://philpapers.org/rec/BIRATP>
10. Fung A. Is democracy too much trouble in a pandemic? In: Smith G, Hughes T, Adams L, Obijiaku C, editors. *Democracy in a Pandemic*. London: University of Westminster Press; 2021. <https://www.uwestminsterpress.co.uk/site/books/e/10.16997/book57/>
11. Bretthauer M, Helsing LM, Løberg M, Kalager M, Guyatt G. Evidence and precaution for legal health interventions: learning from the Covid-19 pandemic. *Ann Intern Med*. 2021;174(10):1456-7. <https://doi.org/10.7326/m21-2839>
12. World Health Organization. Declaration of Alma-Ata. Geneva: World Health Organization; 1978. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/347879>

13. Moberg J, Lewin S, Munabi-Babigumira S, Oxman AD, Treweek S, eds. SURE Guides for Preparing and Using Evidence-Based Policy Briefs, Version 2.1. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2011.
https://epoc.cochrane.org/sites/epoc.cochrane.org/files/public/uploads/SURE-Guides-v2.1/Collectedfiles/sure_guides.html
14. Tan A, Nagraj SK, Nasser M, Sharma T, Kuchenmüller T. What do we know about evidence-informed priority setting processes to set population-level health-research agendas: an overview of reviews. *Bull Natl Res Cent.* 2022;46(1):6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42269-021-00687-8>
15. Involve. People & Participation: How to put citizens at the heart of decision-making. London: Involve; 2005. <https://www.involve.org.uk/resources/publications/practical-guidance/people-and-participation-how-put-citizens-heart-decision>
16. Lijphart A. Unequal participation: Democracy's unresolved dilemma presidential address, American Political Science Association, 1996. *American political science review.* 1997;91(1):1-14. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2952255>
17. Dacombe R, Parvin P. Participatory democracy in an age of inequality. *Representation.* 2021;57(2):145-57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00344893.2021.1933151>
18. International Association for Public Participation. IAP2 Public Participation Spectrum Denver: International Association for Public Participation; 2007 [Available from: https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.iap2.org/resource/resmgr/pillars/Spectrum_8.5x11_Print.pdf.
19. Oxman AD, Lewin S, Lavis JN, Fretheim A. SUPPORT Tools for evidence-informed health Policymaking (STP) 15: Engaging the public in evidence-informed policymaking. *Health Res Policy Syst.* 2009;7 Suppl 1:S15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1478-4505-7-s1-s15>
20. Nilsen ES, Myrhaug HT, Johansen M, Oliver S, Oxman AD. Methods of consumer involvement in developing healthcare policy and research, clinical practice guidelines and patient information material. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2006(3):CD004563.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd004563.pub2>
21. Alonso-Coello P, Schunemann HJ, Moberg J, Brignardello-Petersen R, Akl EA, Davoli M, et al. GRADE Evidence to Decision (EtD) frameworks: a systematic and transparent approach to making well informed healthcare choices. 1: Introduction. *BMJ.* 2016;353:i2016.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i2016>
22. Moberg J, Oxman AD, Rosenbaum S, Schunemann HJ, Guyatt G, Flottorp S, et al. The GRADE Evidence to Decision (EtD) framework for health system and public health decisions. *Health Res Policy Syst.* 2018;16(1):45. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-018-0320-2>
23. Sharples JM, Oxman AD, Mahtani KR, Chalmers I, Oliver S, Collins K, et al. Critical thinking in healthcare and education. *BMJ.* 2017;357:j2234. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j2234>
24. Baron J. *Thinking and Deciding.* 4th ed. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press; 2008.
25. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for Informed Health Choices: a framework for enabling people to think critically about health claims (Version 2022). IHC Working Paper. 2022. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6611932>
26. Dahlgren A, Furuseth-Olsen K, Rose CJ, Oxman AD. The Norwegian public's ability to assess treatment claims: results of a cross-sectional study of critical health literacy. *F1000Research.* 2021;9(179). <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.21902.2>
27. Wiles LK, Kay D, Luker JA, Worley A, Austin J, Ball A, et al. Consumer engagement in health care policy, research and services: A systematic review and meta-analysis of methods and effects. *PLoS One.* 2022;17(1):e0261808. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0261808>
28. Conklin A, Morris Z, Nolte E. What is the evidence base for public involvement in health-care policy?: results of a systematic scoping review. *Health Expect.* 2015;18(2):153-65.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12038>

29. Crawford MJ, Rutter D, Manley C, Weaver T, Bhui K, Fulop N, et al. Systematic review of involving patients in the planning and development of health care. *BMJ*. 2002;325(7375):1263. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.325.7375.1263>
30. Lloyd N, Kenny A, Hyett N. Evaluating health service outcomes of public involvement in health service design in high-income countries: a systematic review. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2021;21(1):364. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-06319-1>
31. O'Mara-Eves A, Brunton G, McDaid D, Oliver S, Kavanagh J, Jamal F, et al. Community engagement to reduce inequalities in health: a systematic review, meta-analysis and economic analysis. *Public Health Research*. 2013;1(4). <https://doi.org/10.3310/phr01040>
32. Panneer S, Kantamaneni K, Pushparaj RRB, Shekhar S, Bhat L, Rice L, editors. Multistakeholder participation in disaster management—the case of the Covid-19 pandemic. Healthcare; 2021: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute.
33. Macaulay B, Reinap M, Wilson MG, Kuchenmüller T. Integrating citizen engagement into evidence-informed health policy-making in eastern Europe and central Asia: scoping study and future research priorities. *Health Res Policy Syst*. 2022;20(1):11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-021-00808-9>
34. Street J, Duszynski K, Krawczyk S, Braunack-Mayer A. The use of citizens' juries in health policy decision-making: a systematic review. *Soc Sci Med*. 2014;109:1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2014.03.005>
35. Boudjelida A, Mellouli S, Lee J. Electronic citizens participation: Systematic review. Proceedings of the 9th international conference on theory and practice of electronic governance. 2016:31-9. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2910019.2910097>
36. Friess D, Eilders C. A systematic review of online deliberation research. *Policy & Internet*. 2015;7(3):319-39. <https://doi.org/10.1002/poi3.95>
37. Santini RM, Carvalho H. The rise of participatory despotism: a systematic review of online platforms for political engagement. *Journal of Information, Communication and Ethics in Society*. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JICES-02-2019-0016>
38. Jacquet V, van der Does R. The Consequences of Deliberative Minipublics: Systematic overview, conceptual gaps, and new directions. *Representation*. 2021;57(1):131-41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00344893.2020.1778513>
39. Van der Does R, Jacquet V. Small-scale deliberation and mass democracy: A systematic review of the spillover effects of deliberative minipublics. *Political Studies*. 2021:00323217211007278. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F00323217211007278>
40. Synnot A, Hill S, Jauré A, Merner B, Hill K, Bates P, et al. Broadening the diversity of consumers engaged in guidelines: a scoping review. *BMJ Open*. 2022;12(6):e058326. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-058326>
41. McDonnell J. Municipality size, political efficacy and political participation: a systematic review. *Local Government Studies*. 2020;46(3):331-50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03003930.2019.1600510>
42. Boivin A, L'Espérance A, Gauvin FP, Dumez V, Macaulay AC, Lehoux P, et al. Patient and public engagement in research and health system decision making: A systematic review of evaluation tools. *Health Expect*. 2018;21(6):1075-84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12804>
43. Booth A, Clarke M, Dooley G, Gherzi D, Moher D, Petticrew M, et al. The nuts and bolts of PROSPERO: an international prospective register of systematic reviews. *Syst Rev*. 2012;1:2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2046-4053-1-2>
44. Sahoo K, Sahay M, Dubey S, Negi S, Dash G, Nayak S, et al. A systematic review of community engagement and involvement in managing the Covid-19 pandemic in urban slums from a gender perspective in low- and middle-income countries. *PROSPERO*. 2021:CRD42021283599. https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospéro/display_record.php?RecordID=283599

45. Fouladi N, Tchangalova N, Ajayi D, Bonailla L, Lovett C, Liggett S, et al. Covid-19 public health measures and patient and public involvement (PPI) in health and social care research: an umbrella review protocol. PROSPERO. 2022:CRD42022307608.
https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?ID=CRD42022307608
46. Gilmore B, Gerlach N, Bhattacharyya S, Daillo A, de Claro V, Lopes C, et al. A living systematic review of community engagement interventions to support Covid-19 vaccine uptake. PROSPERO. 2022:CRD42022301996.
https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?RecordID=301996
47. Liu G, Yeoh E, Dong D, Chen CP, Yao V. Public health and social measures and community engagement in Covid-19: a systematic review. PROSPERO. 2022:CRD42022333144.
https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?RecordID=333144
48. Baumann LA, Brütt AL. Public and patient involvement (PPI) in health policy decisionmaking on the health system-level: protocol for a systematic scoping review. *BMJ Open*. 2021;11(5):e043650. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-043650>
49. Landry J, von Lieres B. Strengthening Democracy Through Knowledge Mobilization: Participedia—A Citizen-Led Global Platform for Transformative and Democratic Learning. *Journal of Transformative Education*. 2022:15413446221103191.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/15413446221103191>
50. Sterne JA, Hernán MA, Reeves BC, Savović J, Berkman ND, Viswanathan M, et al. ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomised studies of interventions. *BMJ*. 2016;355:i4919. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i4919>
51. Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). Synthesising results when it does not make sense to do a meta-analysis. 2017.
https://epoc.cochrane.org/sites/epoc.cochrane.org/files/public/uploads/Resources-for-authors2017/synthesising_results_when_meta-analysis_does_not_make_sense.pdf
52. Ward DJ, Furber C, Tierney S, Swallow V. Using Framework Analysis in nursing research: a worked example. *J Adv Nurs*. 2013;69(11):2423-31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.12127>
53. Brunton G, Oliver S, Thomas J. Innovations in framework synthesis as a systematic review method. *Res Synth Methods*. 2020;11(3):316-30. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1399>
54. Veri F. Mapping Democratic Innovations: A Bottom-up Empirical Perspective. *Representation*. 2022:1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00344893.2022.2075032>
55. Guyatt G, Oxman AD, Akl EA, Kunz R, Vist G, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 1. Introduction-GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):383-94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.04.026>